

UNIVERSITY OF DELAWARE
**CENTER FOR
COMPOSITE MATERIALS**
Celebrating 50 Years

What 3D Printing Cannot Achieve: *Rethinking Composite Additive Manufacturing*

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Outline

- Motivation: why composites AM?
- State-of-art and industrial observations (vs. my lab case study)
- Challenges and viewpoints
- Our solutions: 3D Fiber Tethering (3DFiT)

Disclaimer

- This presentation is intended solely for academic and informational purposes. The content is based on our experience and understanding of typical applications of the discussed products and technologies.
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Composites

COMPOSITE MATERIAL

A MATERIAL MADE OF REINFORCEMENT AND MATRIX

PARTICLES

SHORT / CHOPPED FIBERS

ENDLESS / CONTINUOUS FIBERS

Structures and Manufacturing

Unidirectional (UD) fibers
(TUFF)

Laminates

Hand lay-up

Automatic placement

Fiber – Provides strength and stiffness, carries the load, excellent strength to weight ratio

Matrix – Transfers load between fibers, provides strength in the z-direction, provides resistance to crack propagation and damage

Additive Manufacturing (AM, 3D Printing)

“Additive manufacturing (AM) is the process of joining materials to make objects from 3D model data, usually layer upon layer, as opposed to subtractive manufacturing methodologies.”

- ASTM international F42 Committee on Additive Manufacturing Technologies, 2009.

Subtractive Manufacturing

Milling
Drilling
Cutting

Additive Manufacturing

FDM
DED
PBF

3D Printing
(Direct Ink Writing)

Hybrid additive
manufacturing

Why Composites Additive Manufacturing?

Question 1: Short vs. Continuous Fiber?

Continuous fiber

- Comparable to metal
- Offer potential for metal replacement in structural applications
- Hand layup, molding, automatic placement

Shear-aligned short fibers

- Comparable to continuous fiber
- Applicable to many manufacturing process and applications

Short fiber

- Polymer enhancer
- Processing offers high throughput and very low cost
- Molding methods (injection, extrusion, compression, resin transfer)

Question 2: Do We Need 3D Composites?

Shell-like composite structure used for airplane fuselage, door panel, and wind turbine blade

Question 3: How To Achieve 3D?

Subtractive Manufacturing

Additive Manufacturing

What Are Composites Additive Manufacturing?

3D Composites “Printing”

In-situ Impregnation

Co-Extrusion with Towpreg

Towpreg Extrusion

In-situ Consolidation

Inline Impregnation

Information source: Alexander Matschinski, Virtual Symposium on AFP and AM, TU Munich, Chair of Carbon Composites (LCC), Sep. 2020.

Thermoplastic
ABS, PLA, PEEK

Thermoset
UV resin, Epoxy

The world's first composite 3D printer

All Images from Internet

Observations from Industry: Case 1

Continuous Fiber Printing

Photos taken at an industry expo

Our Lab Results

- Composites Part B: Engineering 257, 110671
- Composites Part B: Engineering 271, 111179
- Composites Part B: Engineering 291, 112001
- Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing 161, 107121

Observations from Industry: Case 2

3D Printing + Molding

Our Lab Results

Composites Communications 56, 102408

Observations from Industry: Case 3

Aligned Short Fibers for Filament Printing

Printing of microfibrres

Good processing but low mechanical performance
Stiffness/strength of 14 GPa/65 Mpa (V_f 20%)

Printing of continuous fibres

Good mechanical performance but difficult
Stiffness/strength of 50 GPa/700 MPa

Images from Internet

Our Lab Results

- Nature Chemical Engineering, 2 (7), 424-435,2025
- Nano letters 22 (23), 9462-9469
- Advanced Materials 35 (38), 2208230
- Advanced Energy Materials 13 (38), 2301704
- Advanced Functional Materials 34 (51), 2410164
- Nature Communications 15 (1), 1-9
- Science Advances 11 (1), eadr4292

Thermo-mechanical stability of printed 3DBenchy

Heating from room temperature to 500 °C in a furnace
(Heating rate: 10 °C/min)

AM Challenges

Anisotropy in Composites & Additive Manufacturing

- Process anisotropy:**

- Topology optimization
- Weight reduction
- Stress enhancement

AM technology

- Material anisotropy:**

Polymer

Nanoscale

Fiber Reinforced Composites

Structural Anisotropy

Viewpoints

ACS Partner Journal

ACCOUNTS —of materials research—

pubs.acs.org/amrcda

Viewpoint

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 Cite This: <https://doi.org/10.1021/accountsmr.5c00156>

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 Metrics & More

 Article Recommendations

Additive manufacturing (AM), or 3D printing, has fundamentally reshaped part fabrication, transitioning from traditional subtractive methods toward incremental layer-by-layer deposition guided by digital models. This shift offers significant advantages, including reduced material waste, geometric freedom, rapid prototyping, and customization. For structural composites—materials combining high-strength fibers within polymer matrices—AM presents remarkable potential for producing lightweight, high-performance components in aerospace, automotive, sports equipment, and renewable energy sectors. Despite considerable enthusiasm, practical implementation of composite AM remains limited. While polymers and metals have successfully transitioned to industrial-scale additive manufacturing, fiber-reinforced composites continue to be predominantly experimental, confined to

In this context, we identify three interconnected barriers that prevent the full industrialization of composite additive manufacturing (Figure 1). First, achieving mechanical perform-

Figure 1. Three key factors impact composite additive manufacturing.

My Research and Reflection

Concept

Material and Process

Resin impregnation and curing

Dual cure enhanced interlayer bonding

3D Structures

End-effector (Printer Head)

1. Resin Impregnation and Curing

$$K_s = \left[d_1 \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{\mu}} \right] \left[\sqrt{\frac{\epsilon^*}{\lambda}} \sqrt{r_0} \right] \left[\sqrt{\frac{\cos\theta}{2}} \right]$$

where d_1 , γ and μ are the density, surface tension and viscosity of the resin, respectively, ϵ^* is the effective sorption porosity of the sorbent (carbon fiber structure), λ is the average tortuosity factor of the capillaries ($\lambda > 1$), r_0 is the average pore radius (interspace between neighboring carbon fibers) and θ is the contact angle of the interface between resin and carbon fiber.

Matter 2 (6), 1594-1604

2. Dual-Cure, Core-Shell Tow-Preg

Issues:

Shadow effect

Our Strategy:

Dual Cure, IPN at Interlayer

Tow-preg cross-section

3. 3D Printer Head Development

Vs.

3D Printing Still a “2D” Process

CarbonForm

4. Beyond 2D Composites Printing

2021 ARPA-E Open

- End effector
- ✓ Dry fiber
- ✓ In situ impregnation

(image from internet)

- Scaffold

3D Fiber Tethering (3DFiT)

3D Fiber Tethering

Redefining Composite Additive Manufacturing

- True 3D fiber architecture for enhanced load transfer
- High-performance continuous fiber reinforcement
- Supports complex, topology-optimized designs
- Automatic fabrication process for various applications

Mindset Shift: Fiber First

Design for Fiber Composite Additive Manufacturing

Bracket Design and Fabrication

Metal bracket

1. 3D topology optimization

2. Fiber path Eulerianization

4. Automatic process

3. Inverse-designed scaffold

Composite bracket

3D Fiber Tethering (3DFiT)

Topology Optimization Framework for 3DFiT

Fiber Path Winding Planning

- **Eulerian circuit** is a path in a graph that starts and ends at the same node and visits every edge exactly once.
- **Hierholzer's algorithm** is a method to find Eulerian circuits in a graph.

Eulerian path for 3DFit

— Continuous path - - - Backtrack path

- Hierholzer algorithm generates Eulerian paths for fiber winding across nodes
- Beam thickness from topology optimization sets fiber count between nodes
- Fibers are incrementally wound to match structural needs

Prelim Characterizations

Crosshead rate: 0.05 in/min

3DFit Applications

Composite Bicycle frame made using
Continuous Carbon fiber

Bike frame

Drone frame

Vehicle B pillar

Architected structure

3DFit Drone Frame

Drop impact test

Summary

- Introduced a new platform technology for fabricating architected 3D composite structures
- Applied topology optimization to design structurally efficient, anisotropy-aware 3D spatial architectures
- Employed Eulerian circuit and Hierholzer algorithm to generate efficient continuous fiber paths for 3DFiT
- Mindset shift: Fiber First!

Fiber, first!

Outlook

- **Mindset Shift:** Design must evolve from generic AM to composite-specific design, emphasizing anisotropy and fiber-path/load-path alignment.
- **Polymer Chemistry:** Develop AM-tailored resins with rapid curing and strong interlayer bonding—requires innovation in resin and interface design.
- **Robotic Automation:** Enable multi-axis fiber deposition through advanced robotics and real-time adaptive control systems.
- **Computational Design:** Expand topology optimization and path planning tools to account for fiber anisotropy and manufacturing constraints.
- **Intelligent Manufacturing:** Integrate AI, ML, and digital twins with in-situ sensing for real-time defect detection and quality control.

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